

Birth year	Names	First paper	PhD ступінь	Retired	Sex	Characteristics	Life years
1955	Harald Clahsen	1976	1981			German Psycholinguistics	
1955	Okpan Oyeoku	1976	1984		w	Nigerian professor of Ceramics and Industrial Art	
1955	Monica Heller	1976			w	Canadian linguistic anthropologist	
1955	Richard Cohn	1976	1987			American music theorist and Battell Professor of Music Theory	
1955	Eve Sweetser	1976	1984		w	American professor of linguistics	
1955	Patricia A. Turner	1977	1985	2012	w	American folklorist, author and academic	
1955	Beth Levin	1977	1983			American linguist	
1955	Linda L. Layne	1977	1986		w	American anthropologist	
1955	Sam Colop	1978	1994			Guatemalan (Native American) linguist, lawyer, poet, writer, newspaper columnist, promoter of the K'iche' language, and social activis	
1955	Francesco Altimari	1978	1978			Italian scholar in the field of Albanology	
1955	Georgina Born	1978	1989		w	British academic, anthropologist and musician	
1955	Normand Doiron	1979	1987			Canadian Professor of French Literature	
1955	Thomas Ede Zimmermann	1979	1987			German Professor of Formal Semantics (Linguistic SemanticsLinguistic PragmaticsPhilosophy of Language)	
1955	Georges-Jean Pinault	1979	1987			French professor of linguistics	
1955	Eckhard J. Schnabel	1979	1983			German evangelical theologian and professor of the New Testament	
1955	Dirk Geeraerts	1980	1981			Belgian linguist	
1955	S. Legene	1980	1998		w	Dutch Full Professor, head of the department of Art and Culture, History, Antiquity (till 2019)	
1955	Eiríkur Rögnvaldsson	1980	1982			Icelandic linguist	
1955	Anna Siewierska	1980	1985	2011		Polish linguist (Language typology)	1955-2011
1955	Victoria Cirlot	1980			w	Spanish scholar of medieval culture and literature, philologist, translator and editor	
1955	Bruce Hayes	1980	1980			American linguist	
1955	Richard Janko	1980	1980			British Anglo-American classical scholar and the Gerald F. Else Distinguished University Professor of Classical Studies	
1955	Paul Smolensky	1981	1981			American Cognitive studies (phonologist)	

1955	Vladimir Trendafilov	1981	1996		Bulgarian Professor of English Literature (literary critic, poet, translator)	
1955	Maarten Mous	1981	1992		Dutch linguist (professor of African linguistics)	
1955	Тамара Гундорова	1981	1981	w	Ukrainian literary critic and cultural scientist	
1955	Elizabeth Marvin	1981	1988	w	American Professor of Music Theory	
1955	Paul J. Griffiths	1981	1983		British-American the Warren Professor of Catholic Thought	
1955	Alessandro Barchiesi	1982			Italian classicist, specialist on Latin poetry	
1955	Mary Beard	1982	1982	w	British English scholar of Ancient Roman civilization	
1955	Denis Feeney	1982	1982		New Zealand Professor of Classics and Giger Professor of Latin	
1955	Otta Wenskus	1982	1982	w	German philologist and translator	
1955	Kim Sichel	1983	1986	w	American Associate Professor, History of Art and Architecture	
1955	Perry R. Cook	1983	1991		American computer music researcher and professor emeritus of computer science and music	
1955	Joseph L. Scarpaci	1983	1985		American human geographer (Center for the Study of Cuban Culture and Economy)	
1955	Kathleen Bardovi-Harlig	1983	1983	w	American linguist	
1955	Carol A. Chapelle	1983	1985	w	American linguist and the Angela B. Pavitt Professor in English	
1955	Cathy Caruth	1983	1988	w	British the Frank H. T. Rhodes Professor of Humane Letters	
1955	Manfred Malzahn	1983	1983		German Professor of English Literature	
1955	Morton Ann Gernsbacher	1983	1983	w	American the Vilas Research Professor and the Sir Frederic C. Bartlett Professor of Psychology	
1955	Andrew Gray	1983	1983	1999	British anthropologist and activist for the rights of indigenous peoples	1955-1999
1955	Olga Najera-Ramirez	1983	1988	w	American anthropologist (Mexican culture)	
1955	Nicolae Achimescu	1983	1993	2020	Romanian Professor Doctor of History and Philosophy of Religions	1955-2020
1955	Wael Hallaq	1983	1983		Israeli scholar of Islamic law and Islamic intellectual history	
1955	James Elkins	1984	1989		American art historian and art critic	

1955	Ahmad Y. Majdoubeh	1984	1984		Jordanian Professor of English and American Literature	
1955	Kristiina Ross	1984	1984	w	Estonian translator	
1955	Smadar Lavie	1984	1989	w	American-Israeli anthropologist, author, and activist	
1955	Jonathan M. Marks	1984	1984		American biological anthropologist	
1955	Philomena Essed	1984	1990	w	Dutch Professor of Critical Race, Gender and Leadership Studies	
1955	Katrina Alicia Karkazis	1985	1985	2017 w	American anthropologist and advocate of breastfeeding	
1955	Clinton Bennett	1985	1990		British-American scholar of religions and participant in interfaith dialogue specialising in the study of Islam and Muslim-non-Muslim encounter	
1955	Katharine Burnett	1986	2005	w	American Professor of Chinese Art History	
1955	Jean Véronis	1986	1988		French linguist, computer scientist and blogger	1955-2013
1955	Noriaki Yusa	1986		w	Japanese linguist	
1955	Maria Bittner	1986	1988	2018 w	American Professor Emerita in Linguistics	
1955	Blake Burleson	1986	1986		American Senior Lecturer in Religion	
1955	Georgina Emma Mary Born	1987	1989	w	British Professor of Music and Anthropology, the granddaughter of the physicist and Nobel laureate Max Born	
1955	Henriette Harich-Schwarzbauer	1987	1987	w	Austrian Professor and Head of the Department of Latin Philology	
1955	Mustafa Majid	1987	2005		Bangladeshi researcher and writer	
1955	Susan C. Herring	1988	1991	w	American linguist and communication scholar	
1955	Maria Damon	1988	1988	w	American Professor of Humanities and Media Studies	
1955	Marie Mulvey-Roberts	1988	1999	w	British Professor in English literature and Reader in Literary Studies	
1955	Efthimia Pandis Pavlakis	1988	1988	w	Greek Professor of Hispanic and Comparative Literature (Latin American Literature, Literature and Economy, Contemporary Spanish Narrative)	
1955	Miguel Ángel Gutiérrez Ávila	1988		2008	Mexican anthropologist	1955-2008
1955	Robin Anne Reid	1989	1992	w	American poet, linguist, and teacher of language and literature	

1955	D. H. Williams	1989	1991		American Professor of Patristics and Historical Theology	
1955	Webb Keane	1990	1990		American anthropologist	
1955	Irena Kossowska	1990	1990	w	Polish art historian	
1955	Beat Weber	1990	1995		Swiss theologian	
1955	Zohar Eitan	1991	1991		Israeli Professor (Music Theory, Music Cognition)	
1955	Babu Suthar	1991			American Gujarati Lecturer in South Asia Studies	
1955	Tami Katz-Freiman	1991		w	Israeli art historian, curator and critic	
1955	Lidija Novakovic	1993	2002	w	Croatian-American Associate Professor of New Testament	
1955	Judith Baxter	1996	2002	2018 w	British sociolinguist and Professor of Applied linguistics	1955-2018
1955	Philippa Hobbs	1997		w	South African art historian, an artist and an art collector	
1955	Antonius Herujiyanto	2000	2000		Indonesian Professor of English and Indonesian literature (literature, BBC-Monitoring, teaching, criticism writing)	
1955	Joseph Muleka	2002	2007		Kenyan Senior Lecturer, Department of Literature (oral, theatre studies, african literature)	
1955	Gilles Massot	2003	No		French multidisciplinary photopainter and academic (based on the idea of "the space between things" aims to establish links and decipher the narratives)	
1955	Joan Fuster Sobrepere	2004	2004		Spanish historian, cultural manager, university professor in art and humanities and Catalan politician	
1955	Louise Fowler-Smith	2009	No	w	Australian Senior Lecturer at College of Fine Arts (eco-painter)	
1955	Agbo Benedict	2011	2015		Nigerian lecturer 1, Department of Music	
1956	Anna Maria Di Sciuillo	1974	1981	w	Canadian professor of Linguistics Department (biolinguistics)	
1956	Jan M. Ziolkowski	1977	1982		American the Arthur Kingsley Porter Professor of Medieval Latin	
1956	James Pustejovsky	1978	1984		American Computational Linguistics	
1956	Volker Zotz	1978	1986		Austrian eminent philosopher, religious studies scholar, Buddhistologist and a prolific author	

1956	William Poser	1979	1985		Canadian-American linguist (historical linguistics of Native American languages)	
1956	Luisa Arvide Cambra	1980	1982	w	Spanish Professor of Arabic and Islamic Studies	
1956	Prof. Dr. H. M. Bahri Ghazali	1980			Indonesian Professor of Comparative Study Of Religion	
1956	Michał Piotr Mrozowicki	1981			Polish Professor of French Literature and Arts	
1956	Ingrid Slavec	1981	1999	w	Slovenian ethnologist	
1956	Eduardo Blasco Ferrer	1981	1981	2017	Spanish-Italian linguist (Paleo-Sardinian and Sardinian language)	1956-2017
1956	Alexis Manaster Ramer	1981	1981		Polish-American linguist	
1956	Lesley Jeffries	1982	1989	w	British Professor of English Language and Linguistics	
1956	Hille Pajupuu	1982	1984	w	Estonian Senior Researcher, Institute of the Estonian Language	
1956	Thomas J. Samuelian	1982			Armenian-American linguist (Armenian language, literature, and history)	
1956	Peter Jan Margry	1982	1985		Dutch historian and European ethnologist	
1956	Evgeny Torchinov	1982	1984	2003	Russian sinologist, Buddhist scholar, professor, and translator	1956-2003
1956	Laura R. Graham	1983	1990	w	American anthropologist	
1956	William Croft	1983	1986		American professor of linguistics	
1956	Manfred Krifka	1983	1986		German linguist	
1956	Anita Rožkalne	1983	1992	w	Latvian literature critic	
1956	Abdalla Uba Adamu	1983	1988		Nigerian academic, educator, publisher and media scholar	
1956	Stephan Koranyi	1983	1983		German philologist, author, lecturer, and an editor	
1956	Grażyna Vetulani	1983	1988	w	Polish philologist and linguist, professor of the humanities	
1956	Ruth Behar	1983	1983	w	Cuban-American anthropologist and writer	
1956	András Kertész	1983	1983		Hungarian linguist	
1956	Frans Wijsen	1983			Dutch professor of practical religious studies	
1956	Catherine Rowett	1983	1987	w	British Professor of Philosophy at the University of East Anglia	

1956	Marina Estela Graça	1984	2003	w	Portuguese assistant Professor at the Department of Software and Media Technology (Animation theories and techniques and Audiovisual communication)		
1956	Yümjiriin Mönkh-Amgalan	1984	1993		Mongolian Professor of Linguistics		
1956	Neil L. Whitehead	1984	1984	2012	British English anthropologist, who is best known for his work on the anthropology of violence, dark shamanism (and Guyanese kanaimà in particular), post-human anthropology and the historical anthropology of South America and the Caribbean	1956-2012	
1956	Jonathan Boyarin	1984	1984		American anthropologist whose work centers on Jewish communities and on the dynamics of Jewish culture, memory and identity		
1956	Isabelle Clark-Decès	1985	1995	2017	w	American professor of anthropology at Princeton University	1956-2017
1956	Βίκυ Πάτσιου	1985	2001	w	Greek Professor of Modern Greek Literature		
1956	Törkenczy Miklós	1985	1994		Hungarian linguist (phonological theory and Hungarian phonology)		
1956	I Dewa Putu Wijana	1985	1995		Indonesian pshycolinguist		
1956	Anthony Pym	1985	1985		Australian Professor of Translation and Intercultural Studies		
1956	Ottmar Ette	1985	1990		German Professor of Romance languages and Comparative literature		
1956	Kim Yeshi	1985	No	w	French-American anthropologist, cofounder the Norbulingka Institute (preserve Tibetan traditions and culture)		
1956	Patricia Sawin	1985	1993	w	American folklorist (informal narrative, festival, folklore theory, and the culture of adoptive families)		
1956	Hélène Cuvigny	1985		w	French papyrologist, specialist of the eastern Egyptian desert in Roman times		
1956	Lynn M. Alexander	1986	1986	w	American Dean of the College of Humanities and Fine Arts		
1956	Stephen Wechsler	1986	1991		American linguistics professor		
1956	Sorin Paliga	1986	1996		Romanian linguist (Russian and Slavic Studies)		
1956	Kenneth Dean	1986	1988		American the Raffles Professor in the Humanities		

1956	Nasser Fakouhi	1986	1993		Iranian anthropologist, writer and translator	
1956	Catherine Virlouvet	1986	1986	w	French historian, a professor of economic and social history of ancient Rome	
1956	Mark Hale	1987	1987		American linguistics professor	
1956	Elizabeth Hume	1987	1992	w	Canadian phonologist	
1956	Tope Omoniyi	1987	1995	2017	Nigerian Professor of Sociolinguistics	1956-2017
1956	Şükrü Halûk Akalın	1987	1987		Turkish linguist and bureaucrat (Head the Turkish Language Association (TLA) from 2001 to 2012)	
1956	Jennifer S. Cole	1987	1987	2016 w	American professor of linguistics (experimental and computational methods to study the sound structure of language)	
1956	Adriana Kaplan Marcusán	1987	1987	w	Argentinian anthropologist and Director of the NGO Wassu Gambia Kafo (WGK) and the Wassu Foundation	
1956	Anagnostis Agelarakis	1987	1989		Greek professor of Anthropological Archaeology and Physical Anthropology	
1956	Anne Stensvold	1987	1992	w	Norwegian professor, history of religions	
1956	Maríbel Fierro	1987		w	Spanish researcher on Middle Eastern studies	
1956	Randy Allen Harris	1988	1990		Canadian Professor of Linguistics, Rhetoric, and Communication Design	
1956	M Dwi Marianto	1988	1998		Indonesian Professor of Fine Arts	
1956	Borut Telban	1988	1994		Slovenian ethnologist	
1956	Zeynep Ergun	1988	1988	w	Turkish full professor at Institute of Social Sciences English Language and Literature	
1956	Richard G. Parker	1988	1988		American professor of sociomedical sciences and of anthropology, arts and sciences	
1956	Knut A. Jacobsen	1988	1994		Norwegian scholar of the history of religions and professor	
1956	Munsi Lampe	1989	1989		Indonesian Lecturer at Department Antropology	
1956	Mira Nábělková	1989	1989	w	Slovakian linguist	
1956	Ramón Mujica Pinilla	1989		2016	Peruvian anthropologist	
1956	Леонід Володимирович Ушкалов	1989	1989	2019	Ukrainian literature critic and writer	1956-2019
1956	Kevin Concannon	1990	2000		American Professor of Art History Director at the School of Visual Arts	

1956	Gheorghe Sarău	1990	1998		Romanian linguist specialized in the Romani language	
1956	Sherman A. Jackson	1990	1990		American the King Faisal Chair in Islamic Thought and Culture and Professor of Religion and American Studies and Ethnicity	
1956	Bonny Norton	1991	1993	w	South African Language and Literacy Education	
1956	Veneeta Dayal	1991	1991	w	American linguist	
1956	Peter Hervik	1991	1992		Danish anthropologist	
1956	Miklós Peternák	1992	1994		Hungarian Professor, Hungarian University of Fine Arts (media art, new media)	
1956	Aado Lintrop	1993	2000		Estonian folklorist, shamanic scholar, singer and poet	
1956	Nan Goggin	1994	No	w	American former director of the Herron School of Art and Design (art, design, multimedia)	
1956	Cathrine Hasse	1994	1996	w	Danish professor of cultural anthropology (intersection between culture, learning and technology)	
1956	Mai Yamani	1995	2004	w	Saudi Arabian independent scholar, author and anthropologist	
1956	Mary Harlow	1995	1995	w	British English archaeologist and classical scholar	
1956	Stephen Akaranga	1996			Kenyan Associate Prof of Religious Studies	
1956	Rosina Lippi-Green	1997	1997	w	American writer	
1956	Alanah Woody	1997	2000	2007 w	American archeologist, anthropologist, professor and executive director of the Nevada Rock Art Foundation	1956-2007
1956	Milena Mileva Blažić	1998	2001	w	Slovenian literary historian and university professor	
1956	Fassih Keiso	1998	2004		Syrian Lecturer in Interior design and contemporary art - Multidisciplinary artist	
1956	Allison Craven	1999	1999	w	Australian the Colin and Margaret Roderick Scholar in Comparative Literature	
1957	Chantal Boulanger	1976		2004 w	French anthropologist who wrote widely on South India and Tamil culture	
1957	Jost Gippert	1977	1977		German linguist, Caucasiologist, author, and professor for Comparative Linguistics at the Institute of Empirical Linguistics	
1957	David Pesetsky	1978	1982	2012	American linguist (Syntax (and interfaces with morphology and semantics); Syntax of Music)	
1957	Gina Conti-Ramsden	1978	1982	2017	Peruvian child language and learning educator	
1957	Bamidele Badejo	1979	1981		Nigerian Professor of Linguistics	

1957	Gina (Regina) Barreca	1979	1979	w	American academic and humorist, Board of Trustees Distinguished Professor of English literature and feminist theory
1957	Max Saunders	1979	1985		British Co-Director of the Centre for Life-Writing Research (modern literature and culture)
1957	Ian Roberts	1979	1985		British generative linguist
1957	Aïcha Ben Abed	1979	1979	w	Tunisian archaeologist and Director of Monuments and Sites at the Institut National du Patrimoine, Tunisia
1957	Heinz-Günther Nesselrath	1980	1981		German philologist
1957	Alessandra Giorgi	1981	1985	w	Italian Professor of Linguistics
1957	Jon Ortiz de Urbina	1981	1986		Spanish (Basque) linguist
1957	Michael Hammond	1981	1984		American linguist (phonology, computational linguistics, syntax)
1957	Nathan E. Bender	1981	No		American Librarian, archivist, folklorist
1957	Fernando Galván	1981	1981		Spanish literary scholar and former Rector / President of the University of Alcalá (2010-2018)
1957	John Bateman	1982	1986		British Professor of Applied Linguistics
1957	Jan Baetens	1982			Belgian poet (Professor of Literary and Cultural Studies)
1957	Ullrich Kockel	1982	1989		German Professor of Cultural Ecology and Sustainability
1957	Ástráður Eysteinnsson	1982	1987		Icelandic Professor of Comparative Literature
1957	András Kornai	1982	1983		Hungarian-American mathematical linguist
1957	Mayfair Yang	1982	1986	w	Taiwanese-American cultural anthropologist of China
1957	Claudio Lomnitz	1982	1987		Columbian the Campbell Family Professor of Anthropology
1957	Anne Berthelot	1982	1982	w	French professor of Medieval French literature and studies
1957	Karl W. Giberson	1982			Canadian Professor of Science & Religion
1957	Peter Ludlow	1982	1985	2015	American philosopher of language
1957	Robin Osborne	1982	1985		British English historian of classical antiquity, who is particularly interested in Ancient Greece
1957	Steven Vertovec	1983	1988		American anthropologist
1957	Peter de Bolla	1983	1983		British Professor of Cultural History and Aesthetics
1957	Peter Wade	1983	1985		British professor of social anthropology

1957	Rosanna Cantavella	1983	1987	w	Spanish professor of Catalan philology (Catalan philology, history of women, Romance philology, medieval rhetorics, digital humanities)
1957	Diane Massam	1983	1985	2017 w	Canadian linguist (syntax of Niuean, Austronesian language)
1957	Kate Burridge	1983	1983	w	Australian linguist
1957	George van Driem	1983	1987		Dutch linguist
1957	Henrietta Moore	1983	1983	w	British social anthropologist
1957	Karl Taube	1983	1988		American Mesoamericanist, archaeologist, epigrapher and ethnohistorian, known for his publications and research into the pre-Columbian cultures of Mesoamerica and the American Southwest
1957	Gregory Hutchinson	1983	1983		British classicist and academic, specialising in Latin literature, Ancient Greek literature, and Latin and Ancient Greek languages
1957	Robert J. Zydenbos	1983	1983		Canadian-Dutch scholar who has doctorate degrees in Indian philosophy and Dravidian studies
1957	Andrew McClellan	1984	1989		American Professor and Museum Studies Advisor
1957	Carol Colatrella	1984	1987	w	American professor of Literature and Cultural Studies
1957	René Kager	1984	1989		Dutch linguist
1957	Yves Porter	1984	1988		French professor of Islamic art history
1957	Paolo Tortonese	1984	1989		Italian Professor of Translation Studies and French Literature
1957	Ghassan Hage	1984	1989		Lebanese-Australian Professor of Anthropology and Social Theory
1957	Laura Janda	1984	1984	w	Norwegian Professor of Russian Linguistics
1957	Alexandra Aikhenvald	1984	1984	w	Russian linguist
1957	Terrell A. Morgan	1984	1984		American linguist and professor of Hispanic linguistics
1957	Jacques Jaubert	1984	1984		French prehistorian and professor of Paleolithic archaeology at University of Bordeaux 1
1957	Hilary M. Carey	1984		w	British Professor of Imperial and Religious History
1957	Mikeal Parsons	1984	1985		American Professor and Macon Chair in Religion
1957	Roger Benjamin	1985	1985		Australian Professor of Art History
1957	Alastair Pennycook	1985	1992		Australian Professor of Language in Education
1957	Monika Wohlrab-Sahr	1985	1991	w	German Professor of Cultural Sociology

1957 Felix K. Ameka	1985	1991		Ghanian socio-cultural cognitive linguistics	
1957 Sigurður Gylfi Magnússon	1985	1993		Icelandic Professor of Cultural History (microhistory)	
1957 Albina Girfanova	1985	1988	2018	Russian linguist and anthropologist	1957-2018
1957 Susanne Küchler	1985	1985	w	German anthropologist and academic, who specialises in material culture	
1957 Badri Yatim	1985			Indonesian Professor of Islamic history and culture	
1957 Kees Hengeveld	1986	1992		Dutch linguist	
1957 Ann Rigney	1986	1987	w	Irish Professor of Comparative Literature	
1957 Bonnie Schwartz	1986	1987	w	American experimental linguist (approaches to second language acquisition)	
1957 Judith McKenzie	1986	1986	2019 w	Australian leading specialist in the art and archaeology of the Middle East	1957-2019
1957 Alexandre Grandazzi	1986	1987		French university professor, a specialist of archaeology and Roman history	
1957 Reimund Bieringer	1986	1986		German theologian, biblical scholar, Professor of New Testament Exegesis at the Faculty of Theology and Religious Studies	
1957 John Bennet	1986	1986		British archaeologist, classicist, and academic, who specialises in the Aegean civilisations	
1957 Sherron Killingsworth Roberts	1987	1987	w	American Professor of Language Arts and Literacy	
1957 Llewellyn Negrin	1987	1988	w	Australian Head of and Senior Lecturer in Art and Design Theory	
1957 Vinko Srhoj	1987	1999		Croatian Full professor in history art	
1957 Гриценко Олександр	1987	1987		Ukrainian poet and cultural scientist	
1957 Petya Yaneva	1987	2000	w	Bulgarian Professor of Classical Philology (Old Church Slavonic, Ancient Greek, Medieval Greek, Textual criticism, e-learning)	
1957 Jakub M. Godzimirski	1987	1987		Polish-Norwegian social anthropologist and international relations scholar	
1957 Lilia Moritz Schwarcz	1987	1993	w	Brazilian historian and anthropologist	
1957 Irene de Jong	1987	1987	w	Dutch classicist and professor of Ancient Greek	
1957 Christian Cannuyer	1987			Belgian historian of religion, professor at the Lille Catholic University,[2][3] a specialist in Coptic Studies and a genealogist	

1957	Ingeborg Bratoeva-Daraktchieva	1988	1988	w	Bulgarian film critic (Contemporary Bulgarian and Balkan film; historical development of film language; film analysis; film criticism)	
1957	Roderic F. Casali	1988	1996		Canadian linguist	
1957	Charlotte Ann Roberts	1988	1988	w	British bioarchaeologist and palaeopathologist, whose research focuses on health and the evolution of infectious disease in humans	
1957	Kathleen M. Adams	1988	1988	w	American cultural anthropologist and an Adjunct Curator at the Field Museum of Natural History	
1957	Єленський Віктор	1988	1989		Ukrainian scholar and public figure, expert in religious studies	
1957	Paul-Gerhard Klumbies	1988	1988		German Protestant theologian and New Testament scholar	
1957	Zakia Zouanat	1989	1989	2012 w	Moroccan anthropologist	1957-2012
1957	Susanne Schröter	1989	1994	w	German Social Anthropologist focussing primarily on Islam, Gender and Conflict Studies	
1957	Claire E. Sterk	1989	1989	w	Dutch scientist and the President of Emory University (positions in anthropology, sociology, and women's, gender, and sexuality studies)	
1957	Charles B Jones	1989			American Associate Professor and Associate Dean in the School of Theology and Religious Studies	
1957	Maria "Masha" Polinsky	1990	1986	w	Russian-American linguist specializing in theoretical syntax	
1957	Alina Pamfil	1990	1990	w	Romanian Professor of literature	
1957	Juhani Klemola	1990	1996		Finnish Professor of English of School of Modern Languages and Translation Studies	
1957	Almut Hintze	1990	1990	w	German academic, philologist, linguist and scholar of Indo-Iranian studies and Zoroastrianism	
1957	Steve Wharton	1991	1995		British Asocoate Professor of French and Communication	
1957	Amir H Zekrgoo	1992	2001		Iranian artist, art historian and Indologist, Professor of Islamic & Oriental Arts	
1957	Roumyana Slabakova	1992	1997	w	Bulgarian Professor of Applied Linguistics	
1957	Enzo Colombo	1993	1998		Italian Professor of Sociology of Culture	

1957 Benny Peiser	1993	1993		Israeli social anthropologist specialising in the environmental and socio-economic impact of physical activity on health	
1957 Matthew Kennedy	1993	No		American writer, film historian, and anthropologist	
1957 Philippe Cornu	1993	1996		French Professeur de bouddhisme, hindouisme, sciences des religions	
1957 Проскурина Елена Николаевна	1994	1999	w	Russian philologist and educator (литературоведения, поэтика русской литературы, автодокументалистика)	
1957 Xinzhong Yao	1994			Chinese professor of chinese religion	
1957 Marijan Richter	1995	2013		Croatian artist, lecturer of fine art	
1957 Irit Meir	1995	1998	2018 w	Israeli linguist (sign languages)	1957-2018
1957 CJP (Nelus) Niemandt	1997	1997		South African Professor Science of Religion and Missiology	
1957 Kahiudi Claver Mabana	1998	1999		Congolese Professor of Francophone African and Caribbean Literature	
1957 Matti Fischer	2001	2004		Israeli Lecturer in Classical Art History (painter)	
1957 Miriam Hall Kirch	2003	2003	w	German Professor of Art History	
1957 AbdulMahmoud Ibrahim	2006	2006		Saudi Arabian Associate Professor of English Language	
1958 Scott Van Duyne	1979	2007		American researcher in Music Theory and Acoustics	
1958 Nick Thieberger	1980	2004		Australian linguist	
1958 Niko Besnier	1980	1986		French-American-New Zealandish Professor of Cultural Anthropology	
1958 Silvia Ronchey	1980	1981	w	Italian Professor of Classical Philology and Byzantine Civilization	
1958 Carolyn Hamilton	1980	1993	w	South African anthropologist and historian who is a specialist in the history and uses of archives	
1958 Nedzad Ibrahimovic	1981	1981		Bosnian Professor of Film Theory and Theory of Literature (writer, literature and film critic, screenwriter and documentary filmmaker)	
1958 Basilio Gichobi Mungania	1981	2018		Kenyan lecturer and research consultant in Swahili linguistics	
1958 Ekaterina Rakhilina	1981		w	Russian linguist	

1958	Betsy Stirratt	1982	No	w	American artist, gallery director of Grunwald Gallery of Art	
1958	Joanna Tokarska-Bakir	1982	1993	w	Polish cultural anthropologist, literary scholar, and religious studies scholar	
1958	Máirín Nic Eoin	1982	1996	w	Irish academic and scholar (Literature in Irish)	
1958	Gregory Laden	1982	1992		American biological anthropologist and science blogger	
1958	Christian Mair	1983	1985		Austrian linguist	
1958	Марина Александровна Можейко	1983	1983	w	Belarusian philosopher and culturologist	
1958	David Zeitlyn	1983	1990		British social Anthropologist	
1958	Rodica Zafiu	1983	1998	w	Romanian linguist	
1958	Alex Alsina	1983	1993		Spanish researcher in Translation and Language	
1958	Wendy Ayres-Bennett	1983	1983	w	British linguist, Professor of French Philology and Linguistics	
1958	Susan Rothstein	1983	1983	2019 w	British-Israeli linguist	1958-2019
1958	Anne Vainikka	1984	1989	2018 w	American linguist (syntax of second language acquisition)	1958-2018
1958	Marc Leman	1984	1991		Belgian musicologist	
1958	Christopher Mccully	1984	1988		British scholar in Department of Literature, Film and Theatre Studies	
1958	Milena Kirova	1984	1986	w	Bulgarian Professor in Bulgarian Literature and Gender Studies	
1958	Maxim Krongauz	1984			Russian linguist	
1958	Jose Maria Parreño	1984	1995		Spanish poet, cultural manager, university professor, exhibition curator and Spanish art critic	
1958	Rita Franceschini	1984	1992	w	Swiss linguist	
1958	Toon van Meijl	1985	1991		Dutch professor of cultural anthropology	
1958	Harald Baayen	1985	1989		Dutch quantitative linguist	
1958	Lenore A. Grenoble	1985	1986	w	American linguist specializing in Slavic and Arctic Indigenous languages	
1958	Dieter Vieweger	1985	1985		German Biblical scholar and Prehistorian Archaeologist	
1958	Elsbeth Probyn	1986	1989	w	Australian academic (Professor of Gender and Cultural Studies)	

1958 Brett Millier	1986	1986	w	British the Reginald L. Cook Professor of American Literature	
1958 Jaan Undusk	1986	1986		Estonian specialist in literature and writer	
1958 Elly van Gelderen	1986	1986	w	Dutch the Regents' Professor in the Department of English/Linguistics concentration	
1958 Csaba Földes	1986	1987		Hungarian linguist (contemporary German language and German as a foreign language)	
1958 Louise Burkhart	1986	1986	w	American academic ethnohistorian and anthropologist, noted as a scholar of early colonial Mesoamerican literature	
1958 David Tab Rasmussen	1986	1986	2014	American biological anthropologist	1958-2014
1958 David B. Gowler	1986	1989		British the Pierce Chair of Religion	
1958 John M. G. Barclay	1986	1986		British biblical scholar, historian of early Christianity, and academic	
1958 Tarek Swelim	1987	1994		Egyptian art historian, Associate Prof. Of Islamic Art and Architecture	
1958 Abdel-Rahman Abu-Melhim	1987	1992		Jordanian-American Full Professor of English Language and Literature	
1958 Nicasio Urbina	1987	1987		Nicaraguan writer, professor and critic	
1958 Regina Bendix	1987	1987	w	Swiss-German professor of European Ethnology	
1958 Edward Vajda	1987	1987		American linguist (Ket language, historical linguistics, Na-Dené languages, comparative linguistics)	
1958 Toby Miller	1988	1991		British-Australian-American interdisciplinary social scientist (cultural studies and media studies)	
1958 Stjepko Rupčić	1988	No		Croatian art educator, Professor of art history	
1958 Ahmed Sokarno Abdel-Hafiz	1988	1988		Egyptian Dean of Faculty of Art (linguist)	
1958 Jae Jung Song	1988	1990	2017	New Zealand scholar (linguistic typology)	1958-2017
1958 Annemarie Mol	1988	1989	w	Dutch ethnographer and philosopher, Professor of Anthropology of the Body	
1958 Thomas Blom Hansen	1988			Danish anthropologist and leading contemporary commentator on religious and political violence in India	
1958 Michael E. Harkin	1988	1988		American one of the leading anthropologists in the United States specializing in the ethnohistory of indigenous people of the western U.S. and Canada	

1958	Alissandra Cummins	1988		w	Barbadian the leading experts on Caribbean heritage, museum development and art
1958	Peter C. Herman	1989	1990		American Professor of English Literature (expert on Shakespeare and Milton)
1958	Emil Hilje	1989	1993		Croatian Professor of Art History
1958	Deddy Mulyana	1989	1996		Indonesian Professor of Communication Studies
1958	Kristen Gremillion	1989	1989	w	American anthropologist whose areas of specialization include paleoethnobotany, origins of agriculture, the prehistory of eastern North America, human paleoecology and paleodiet, and the evolutionary theory
1958	Joseph Alter	1989	1989		American medical anthropologist known for his research into the modern practice of yoga as exercise
1958	Simber Atay	1990	1990	w	Turkish lecturer of Faculty of Fine Arts, Department of Photography and Department of Film Design
1958	Anders Aschim	1990	2010		Norwegian priest, professor, religious education
1958	Jussi Pakkasvirta	1991	1997		Finnish Professor of Area and Cultural Studies
1958	George Grigore	1991	1997		Romanian writer, essayist, translator, professor, researcher in Middle Eastern Studies
1958	Ēvalds Daugulis	1991	2002		Latvian Professor of Music Arts
1958	Judith Berman	1991	1991	w	American (Idaho Native) anthropologist and writer of science fiction and fantasy
1958	Edmund Herzig	1991	1991		British he Soudavar Professor of Persian Studies of the faculty of Oriental studies
1958	Asma Afsaruddin	1991	1993	w	American Professor in the Department of Near Eastern Languages and Cultures
1958	Christian Delporte	1991	1991		French historian specialized in political and cultural history of France in the twentieth century, including the history of media, image and political communication
1958	Mohamed Diriye Abdullahi	1992	2001		Somali-Canadian scholar, linguist, writer, translator and professor.
1958	Omomia O. Austin	1992	2015		Nigerian Senior Lecturer, Philosophy of Religion
1958	Aninhalli Vasavi	1993	1993	w	Indian Social Anthropologist and an Independent Researcher
1958	Rotimi Williams Omotoye	1993	2000		Nigerian Professor of Religions (Christian Studies)

1958	Marisa Keuris	1994	2006	w	South African literary scholar, theatre researcher and academic
1958	Helena Saarikoski	1994	1995	w	Finnish Adjunct Professor of Folklore and Women's Studies
1958	Niloofer Haeri	1994	1994	w	Iranian-American professor in the Department of Anthropology
1958	Laurens ten Kate	1994	1994		Dutch the Endowed professor Liberal Religion & Humanism
1958	Laura Otilia Vasiliu	1995	1995	w	Moldovan Musicologist
1958	Caroline Vercoe	1995	2008	w	New Zealand Senior Lecturer in Art History (Contemporary New Zealand and Pacific Art, issues of Gender and Postcolonial Theory)
1958	Lidija Merenik	1995	1999	w	Serbian Professor of Art History
1958	Ирина Петровна Павлова	1996	1998		Russian Head of Department Department of General Linguistics and Rhetoric, Yakutsk
1958	Eda Kalmre	1996	2007	w	Estonian senior researcher (folklore, legend, contemporary legend, rumour, history)
1958	Saeed Bozorg Bigdeli	1996	1996		Iranian Professor of Persian Language and Literature
1958	Mihaela Sanda Salontai	1997	2001	w	Romanian art historian
1958	Vasile Spiridon	2001	2003		Romanian Professor of Romanian Literature, writer
1958	Vedada Baraković	2003		w	Bosnian assistant professor of Faculty of Social Sciences and Humanities
1958	Muharrem Gashi	2004	2015		Albanian assistant of Professor in linguistics
1959	Alec Marantz	1978	1981		American linguist and researcher in the fields of syntax, morphology, and neurolinguistics
1959	Paul Boersma	1979	1998		Dutch Professor of Phonetic Sciences
1959	Mark Baker	1981	1985		American linguist
1959	Deborah Wong	1981	1991	w	American academic, educator, and public musicologist
1959	Michele Cometa	1982	1986		Italian Professor of Comparative Literature and Visual Culture
1959	Bernardo Arriaza	1982			Chilean physical anthropologist with an emphasis on bioarchaeology

1959 Nancy Abelmann	1982	1990	w	American anthropologist and Harry E. Preble Professor of anthropology, Asian American studies, and East Asian languages and cultures	1959-2016
1959 Stephen Goddard	1983	1983		American specialist in the history of printmaking	
1959 Christophe Den Tandt	1983	1994		Belgian Professor of English and American Literatures	
1959 Victoria D. Alexander	1983	1990	w	British Professor of Sociology and Arts Management	
1959 Nikolaus P. Himmelmann	1983	1986		German linguist	
1959 Tamás Mohay	1983	1993		Hungarian Professor of ethnography and cultural anthropology	
1959 Akhil Gupta	1983	1988		Indian anthropologist (PhD Eng)	
1959 Angelos Chaniotis	1983	1984		Greek philologist, historian and Classics scholar (cultural, religious, legal and economic history of the Hellenistic period and the Roman East)	
1959 Diane Lillo-Martin	1983	1986	w	American Board of Trustees Distinguished Professor of Linguistics (signed languages)	
1959 LouAnn Gerken	1983	1987	w	American Professor of Psychology, Linguistics, and Cognitive Science	
1959 Jocelyne Dakhli	1983	1990	w	Tunisian-French historian and anthropologist	
1959 Reinhold F. Gleis	1983	1983		German philologist and translator	
1959 Bernard Coulie	1983	1985		Belgian academic specializing in Greek patristic literature primarily of Late Antiquity and its derivatives (hence an expertise in translation techniques) and counterparts in eastern Christian oriental languages of that period (notably Armenian, Syriac and Georgian)	
1959 Dejan Ajdačić	1983	2000		Serbian Slavist, philologist, folklorist, ethnolinguist, literary critic, translator and editor	
1959 Leif Stenberg	1983	1996		Swedish Dean of the Institute for the Study of Muslim Civilisations	
1959 Sten Vikner	1984	1995		Danish linguist	
1959 Drew Westen	1984			American professor in the Departments of Psychology and Psychiatry	
1959 Thomas Keenan	1985	1990		American author, educator, and scholar(media and conflict, literary and political theory, and violence and politics)	

1959	Patricia A. Duff	1985	1993	w	Canadian Professor of Language and Literacy Education
1959	Seyfi Başkan	1985	1998		Turkish art historian
1959	Peter Lasersohn	1985	1988		American professor of linguistics
1959	Tomas Staffan Riad	1985	1992		Swedish linguist, specialised in Swedish phonology and prosody
1959	Sabina Magliocco	1985	1988	w	American professor of Anthropology and Religion
1959	Ann Copestake	1986	1992	w	British Computational Linguistics
1959	Gerasimos Zoras	1986	1991		Greek Professor of Italian Literature
1959	Tibor Laczkó	1986	1986		Hungarian linguist, Director of Institute of English and American Studies
1959	Uriagereka	1986	1986		Spanish biolinguist
1959	Michelle P. Brown	1986		2013 w	British Professor Emerita of Medieval Manuscript Studies at the School of Advanced Study
1959	Arthur Versluis	1986	1990		American professor and Department Chair of Religious Studies in the College of Arts & Letters
1959	Ilkka Pyysiäinen	1986	1993		Finnish doctor of theology, whose research has focused on cognitive science of religion
1959	Chris Atton	1987	1999		British Professor of Media and Culture
1959	Božena Bednaříková	1987	1998	w	Czech associate professor and the chair of postgradual doctoral study programme Czech Language
1959	Henkjan Honing	1987	1991		Dutch Professor of Music Cognition (Music Cognition, Music Perception, Music Psychology, Musicality, Music Technology)
1959	Reinhard Kopiez	1987	1990		German Professor for Music Psychology
1959	Denis Ekpo	1987	1987		Nigerian professor of Comparative Literature
1959	Rocio De La Villa	1987	1987	w	Spanish Professor of Aesthetics and Theory of Art
1959	Roger Lancaster	1987	1987		American professor of anthropology and cultural studies
1959	Kjersti Bale	1987	1987	w	Norwegian professor at the Department of Literature, Area Studies and European Languages
1959	Allen Hirson	1987	1992		British Senior Lecturer in Phonetics
1959	Xaverio Ballester	1987	1987		Spanish linguist

1959	Izabela Maria Furtado Kestler	1987	1992	2009	w	Brazilian professor of German studies	1959-2009
1959	Lynne Joyrich	1988	1990		w	American Professor of Modern Culture and Media	
1959	Carolynne Larrington	1988			w	British scholar of medieval literature and author	
1959	Bernd J. Kröger	1988	1989			German phonetician	
1959	Steven M Demorest	1988	1989	2019		American Professor of Music	1959-2019
1959	Ineke Sluiter	1988	1990		w	Dutch classicist and professor of Greek Language and Literature	
1959	Birgit Heller	1988	1988		w	Austrian Professor of Religious Studies	
1959	Ian Syson	1989	1993			Australian Senior Lecturer (history of Australia's football codes, particularly soccer)	
1959	Raymattja Marika	1989	No	2008		Australian Yolngu aboriginal leader, scholar, educator, translator, linguist and cultural advocate	1959-2008
1959	Frederik Woudhuizen	1989	2006			Dutch independent scholar (ancient Indo-European languages, hieroglyphic Luvian/Luwian, and Mediterranean protohistory)	
1959	Catherine L. Besteman	1989	1991		w	American anthropologist and holds the position of Francis F. Bartlett and Ruth K. Bartlett Professor of Anthropology	
1959	Anne Dambricourt-Malassé	1989	1989	2014	w	French paleoanthropologist at the French National Centre for Scientific Research (CNRS)	
1959	Sarah J. Mahler	1989	1992		w	American author and cultural anthropologist	
1959	Kellie Jones	1989	1999		w	American Professor in Art History and Archaeology and the Institute for Research in African American Studies (IRAAS)	
1959	Klaas Tindemans	1989	1996			Dutch Professor of Theatre & Cultural History	
1959	Bernd Möbius	1990	1993			German Professor of Phonetics and Phonology	
1959	Colleen Denney	1990	1990		w	American Professor of Art History and Gender and Women's Studies at University of Wyoming	
1959	Ovidiu Pecican	1990	1998			Romanian Professor of History of European Culture and Civilisation	
1959	Michael Minkov	1991	2010			Bulgarian linguist	
1959	Dejan Ajdačić	1991	2000			Serbian Slavist, philologist, folklorist, ethnolinguist, literary critic, translator and editor	

1959	Brian J. McVeigh	1991	1991		American theorist of cultural psychology and historical changes in human mentality
1959	Markus Vinzent	1991	1991		German historian of religion (specializing in early Christianity, Patristics and Medieval Studies, Historiography, Retromodernity, Religion and Business)
1959	Päivi Pahta	1992	1998	w	Finnish linguist (Professor of English Philology)
1959	Adams Bodomo	1992	1997		Ghanaian professor of African Studies (African Languages and Literatures)
1959	Rosario Monteiro	1992	1997	w	Portuguese Professor of Comparative Literature
1959	Anna Novakov	1992	1992	w	Serbian-American art historian, critic, educator, and curator (history of art, gender and visual culture)
1959	Montserrat Batllori Dillet	1992	1995	w	Spanish Senior Lecturer in Spanish Language (Diachrony)
1959	Rijk van Dijk	1992	1997		Dutch Professor of Religion in Contemporary Africa and its Diaspora
1959	Spyridon Tsitsigkos	1992	2002		Greek Associate Professor of Psychology of Religion
1959	I Ketut Jirnaya	1993	2011		Indonesian linguist
1959	Manfred L. Pirner	1993	1997		German Professor of Religious Education
1959	Desmond Ayim-Aboagye	1993	1993		Ghanaian Professor of Psychology of Religion
1959	Sean Homer	1994	1994		British Professor of Film and Literature
1959	Petri Heikki Toiviainen	1995	1996		Finnish Professor of Music
1959	Shaun Belcher	1996	No		British Freelance Art Researcher (Multi-Disciplinary Painter with specialist Transmedia Focus)
1959	Karen Poe	1996	2007		Costa Rican Full Professor of Literature and Cinema
1959	Anne Maria Makkonen	1996	2007	w	Finnish affiliated researcher in The Performing Arts Research Centre, Theatre
1959	Ildikó Ungvari Zrínyi	1996	1999	w	Hungarian theater writer, literary translator, university lecturer
1959	Katherine Patricia Mary Barber	1998	No	w	Canadian lexicographer, former Editor-in-Chief of the Canadian Oxford Dictionary
1959	Mohammad Behnamfar	1999	1999		Iranian professor of Persian language and literature
1959	Аюпова Роза Алляметдиновна	2000	2001	w	Russian philologist and educator (сопоставительное языкознание, лексикография, фразеология)

1959 Fatimayin Foluke	2002	2010	w	Nigerian Senior Lecturer of Language Education and Applied Linguistics
1959 Paul Doornbusch	2002	2010		Australian composer and musician, Researcher on algorithmic composition and electronic music
1959 Anthony Linden Jones	2009	2019		Australian composer, conductor and performer